

1 **Kuroshio Extension and Gulf Stream dominate the Eddy Kinetic Energy intensification**
2 **observed in the Global Ocean**

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9
10 **Abstract**

11 Ocean mesoscale variability, including meanders and eddies, is a crucial component of the
12 global ocean circulation. The Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE) of these features accounts for about
13 90% of the ocean's total kinetic energy. This study investigates if the global ocean mesoscale
14 variability is becoming more energetic by analyzing 30 years of satellite altimetric observations.
15 We use two observational products: one constructed from a consistent pair of altimeters and
16 another including all available missions. Our results reveal a significant global EKE strengthening
17 of 1-3% per decade. The intensification is concentrated in energetic regions, particularly in the
18 Kuroshio Extension and the Gulf Stream, which show EKE increases of ~50% and ~20%,
19 respectively, over the last decade. These observations raise new questions about the impact of
20 the Gulf Stream strengthening on the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC) and
21 challenge existing climate models, emphasizing the need for improved representation of small-
22 scale ocean processes.

24 Introduction

25 Earth has undergone anthropogenic global warming driven by the emissions of greenhouse
26 gasses that have been released to the atmosphere by human activities since the beginning of
27 the Industrial Revolution (Cubasch et al., 2013). The ocean is the major Earth's heat reservoir
28 and has absorbed 90% of the anthropogenic excess heat (IPCC, 2019). Ocean circulation plays a
29 key role in the global climate system by redistributing water masses and their properties,
30 including heat and carbon, throughout the global ocean. At the same time, changes in the
31 climate system have not only warmed the upper ocean but also altered the wind stress, heat,
32 and freshwater fluxes that act as driving forces for ocean circulation (IPCC, 2007; IPCC, 2019).
33 Hence, climate change can modify the intricate system that constitutes the global ocean
34 circulation (Beal & Elipot, 2016; Toggweiler & Russell, 2008; Yang H. et al., 2020). The mesoscale
35 circulation, defined as those motions with spatial scales between ~ 10 -100 km, is an essential
36 component of the global ocean circulation and is in many ways dynamically analogous to
37 atmospheric weather (McGillicuddy, 2016). It is constituted by a time-mean (or steady) flow
38 and a time-varying flow, which we will refer here as the mesoscale variability and includes
39 meanders and eddies. These features exist throughout the global ocean and transport and mix
40 water masses and their properties over long distances and locally in depth, influencing larger
41 and smaller-scale processes (Chelton et al., 2011; McGillicuddy, 2016). The kinetic energy
42 associated with the mesoscale variability (called Eddy Kinetic Energy, EKE) represents about
43 90% of the total kinetic energy of the oceans (Ferrari and Wunsch, 2009; Wunsch, 2007),
44 making these features an essential component of the ocean circulation. Here, we aim to
45 evaluate if the global ocean mesoscale variability is changing over the altimetric era through the
46 analysis of global trends in EKE, which is a metric commonly used to determine the intensity of
47 ocean currents. Providing knowledge on this topic is crucial for predicting the future state of
48 our oceans and their role in the broader climate system.

49 Recently, several investigations have been exploring this subject using datasets that may have
50 limitations for long-term analyses (Hu et al., 2020; Martínez-Moreno et al., 2021; Pujol et al.,
51 2023; Wunsch, 2020). These studies employ data products with an inconsistent number of

52 observations over time, potentially introducing erroneous trends to the evaluated variables
53 (Bengtsson et al., 2004; Pascual et al., 2006). The ocean currents of these products are derived
54 from sea level measurements collected over the last three decades by a constellation of
55 satellite altimeters with a varying number of missions that range from two to seven (Fig. S1).
56 The inclusion of new satellites over time enhances the capacity to map mesoscale structures,
57 despite the time-variable errors dependent on the number of satellites used. The altimetric
58 gridded product obtained from these observations has been essential to understand the large-
59 scale and mesoscale ocean circulation (Abdalla et al., 2021; Morrow et al., 2023), and a
60 continuous effort is done to improve its resolution and accuracy, for instance with updated
61 corrections and mapping parameters or techniques (Pujol et al., 2016; Taburet et al., 2019; Le
62 Traon et al., 2019; Ubelmann et al., 2021; Ballarotta et al., 2023; among others), and with new
63 satellites such as the recently launched Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission
64 (Morrow et al., 2019; Fu et al., 2024; Ballarotta et al., 2024). An additional altimetric product is
65 constructed for climate applications (Taburet et al., 2019). This product includes observations
66 from a consistent pair of altimeters, which is considered the minimum requirement for
67 resolving mesoscale features (Pascual et al., 2006), and prioritizes the stability of the global
68 mean sea level assuming the cost of reducing the spatial resolution. A constant number of
69 altimeters ensures almost uniform errors over the altimetric era, with minor variations due to
70 changes in the satellite constellation (Pujol et al., 2023). In consequence, this altimetric product
71 is focused on the analysis of the long-term evolution of sea level, being appropriate for climate
72 applications (Taburet et al., 2019).

73 This study aims to assess if the global ocean mesoscale variability is becoming more energetic
74 through the analysis of 30 years of altimetric data (1993-2022), paying special attention to
75 regions characterized by intense mesoscale activity (Fig. 1). To address this objective, we
76 evaluate global trends of EKE computed from altimetric observations provided by the climatic
77 product (herein *two-sat*) and also by the product that includes all available altimeter missions
78 (herein *all-sat*) to estimate the impact of the increasing number of satellites on the results.

79

80 **Fig. 1. Mean EKE and high EKE regions.** (A) Global map of the temporally averaged EKE field
 81 computed over the period 1993-2022 at each grid point ($1/4^\circ$ of spatial resolution) for the *all-*
 82 *sat* altimetric product. Green contours outline the high EKE regions and cyan lines delimit the
 83 tropical band. Black oblique lines indicate the areas masked due to ice coverage throughout the
 84 annual cycle. (B) Map showing the high EKE regions. GWSE: Great Whirl and Socotra Eddy in
 85 East Africa, AC: Agulhas Current, KE: Kuroshio Extension, EAC: East Australian Current, GS: Gulf
 86 Stream, LC: Loop Current, BMC: Brazil-Malvinas Confluence region.

87 **Results**

88 **Global Eddy Kinetic Energy trends**

89 The trends of the globally-averaged EKE time series over the altimetric era (1993-2022) are
 90 positive and statistically significant at the 95% confidence level for both altimetric products,
 91 with a large difference in magnitude (Fig. 2A, C). The trend of the *all-sat* EKE time series is 0.64
 92 $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$ (or $0.066 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ year}^{-1}$), while the trend of the *two-sat* EKE time series is $0.19 \text{ cm}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$

93 (or $0.019 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ year}^{-1}$), i.e., 3.4 times smaller (Fig. 3C). These EKE trends represent an increase
94 per decade of 2.8% for *all-sat* and 0.8% for *two-sat*, relative to their respective mean EKE values
95 (Table S1). Assuming an area of the surface global ocean of $3.28 \times 10^8 \text{ km}^2$, the area-integrated
96 EKE trend is $0.22 \times 10^{15} \text{ J m}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ for the *all-sat* product and $0.06 \times 10^{15} \text{ J m}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ for
97 the *two-sat* product. The result obtained from the *all-sat* altimetric product may suggest that
98 the ocean mesoscale variability is experiencing a strong intensification (Hu et al., 2020;
99 Martínez-Moreno et al., 2021). However, the different result obtained from the *two-sat*
100 product, which is based on the observations gathered by a consistent number of satellites,
101 suggests that the larger *all-sat* EKE trend may be, at least partially, an artifact induced by the
102 increasing number of satellites in the altimetric record (Pujol et al., 2023; Wunsch, 2020) (Fig.
103 S1). The inclusion of additional satellites within the altimetric record can enhance the capacity
104 to detect higher energy levels. Consequently, a progressive increase in the satellite count over
105 time may give rise to an increase of energy attributed to this phenomenon. Another reason for
106 this difference could be that *two-sat* may not completely capture a potential increase in
107 mesoscale kinetic energy due to its lower resolution. Hence, both altimetric products support
108 the conclusion that the global ocean mesoscale variability is becoming more energetic over the
109 altimetric era, although the magnitude may be overestimated by *all-sat* and underestimated by
110 *two-sat*.

111

112 **Fig. 2. EKE time series and trends.** Area-weighted mean EKE time series computed over (A) the
 113 global ocean and (B) the high EKE regions, for the *all-sat* (red line) and *two-sat* (blue line)
 114 altimetric products. Thinner lines represent the original data, while thicker lines show the
 115 yearly-rolling mean (i.e. 365-day-window moving average). (C) Trends of the original area-
 116 weighted mean EKE time series shown in (A, B), computed from 1993 to 2022. All trends are
 117 statistically significant (p < 0.05). Standard errors are shown with yellow (blue) error bars for *all-*
 118 *sat* (*two-sat*).

119 A sensitivity test reveals that the ratio between the global *all-sat* EKE trend and the global *two-*
 120 *sat* EKE trend is reduced from 3.4 between 1993-2022 to 1.8 when computed for the period
 121 2000-2022, and this value is maintained or slightly smaller for the periods evaluated afterwards
 122 (Fig. 3A, C). The year 2000 marks the division between two distinct periods in the altimetry era:
 123 an initial period characterized by a varying number of satellites ranging from 2 to ~3, followed
 124 by a second period where the number of satellites was consistently higher than 2 (with the
 125 exception of one month in 2008) (Fig. S1). This result indicates that the difference between *all-*

126 *sat* and *two-sat* EKE trends is partly related to the varying number of satellites included to build
127 the *all-sat* product, and this difference is higher when computing trends over the complete
128 altimetry era and reduced, but still important, when computing trends after 2000.

129 A striking feature is that *two-sat*, whose limitations are not time-dependent, show a clear
130 increase of the global EKE trend for the periods evaluated in the sensitivity test (Fig. 3A).
131 Considering the complete altimetric era, the global *two-sat* EKE trend is $0.19 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, but this
132 trend gets larger when shortening the time series, to a maximum of $1.19 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ over 2012-
133 2022. Hence, both altimetric products reveal an intensification of the global ocean mesoscale
134 variability, and *two-sat* demonstrates that this increase in EKE is much faster when evaluating
135 the last two decades. The EKE trend computed over 2012-2022 for *two-sat* is 6.2 times larger
136 than the trend computed over 1993-2022, while for *all-sat* this ratio is only 2.2 (Fig. 3A). The
137 smaller ratio for *all-sat* is related to the impact that the varying number of satellites included in
138 this product has on the computation of EKE trends. When considering the complete altimetric
139 era, the number of satellites drastically changes from ~ 2 satellites between 1993-2000, to ~ 3 -4
140 satellites between 2000-2016, and to higher than 4 satellites after 2016 (Fig. S1). This increase
141 over time on the number of satellites implies an enhancement on the capacity to detect energy.
142 A progressive increase on the satellite count could lead to an increase of the energy observed
143 related to this phenomenon, rather than a real increase of energy in the ocean. This
144 circumstance would result in an overestimation of the EKE trends computed from *all-sat*.
145 However, this overestimation diminishes when analyzing shorter, more recent time periods,
146 because this phenomenon decreases if we exclude the first years of data computed from only
147 ~ 2 satellites.

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149 **Fig. 3. Sensitivity test.** EKE trends computed over the (A) global ocean and (B) high EKE regions
 150 for different periods. Statistically significant trends ($p < 0.05$) are represented by solid-colored
 151 bars, while non-significant trends are represented as bars with oblique lines. Standard errors

152 for *all-sat* (*two-sat*) trends are shown with yellow (blue) error bars. (C) Ratio of the *all-sat* EKE
153 trend divided by the *two-sat* EKE trend.

154 Martínez-Moreno et al. (2021) reported a trend of the global surface area-integrated EKE of
155 $(0.09 \pm 0.04) \cdot 10^{15} \text{ J m}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ using a previous version (vDT2018) of the *all-sat* altimetric
156 product and following a similar methodology but computing trends over the period between 1
157 January 1993 to 7 March 2020 and from a smoothed 365-day running average time series. The
158 *all-sat* EKE trend computed here over 1993-2022 from the currently available vDT2021 version
159 is 2.4 times that value (Fig. 2). We have also calculated the *all-sat* EKE trend over the same
160 period as Martínez-Moreno et al. (2021) and over a 365-day running average (Fig. S2), without
161 finding large differences with respect to the trends calculated from the original data over 1993-
162 2022 (Fig. 2). This suggests that the discrepancy between the trends computed in this study and
163 the trends reported by Martínez-Moreno et al. (2021) is related to the version of the product
164 used. We cannot test this sensitivity because the *all-sat* vDT2018 altimetric product is no longer
165 available. However, the *two-sat* vDT2018 altimetric product is still available on the Copernicus
166 Climate Change Service (C3S) website ([10.24381/cds.4c328c78](https://climate.copernicus.eu/c3s-4c328c78)) and we have found high
167 sensitivity in the results related to the version of the product analyzed (Fig. S3). Indeed, a global
168 non-significant EKE trend of $-0.002 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ was obtained for the *two-sat* vDT2018 altimetric
169 product in comparison to the $0.114 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ non-significant trend obtained for the same
170 period with *two-sat* vDT2021 (Fig. S3).

171 **Eddy Kinetic Energy trends over regions of intense mesoscale activity**

172 The mesoscale variability intensification is clearly concentrated in regions characterized by high
173 EKE levels (Fig. 1, 2, S4). In contrast, the Tropics and the rest of the ocean exhibit predominantly
174 statistically non-significant trends in the averaged EKE time series (Fig. S4). The distinct peaks
175 detected in global and tropical time series, approximately corresponding to 1998 and 2016,
176 were previously identified as El Niño events (Martínez-Moreno et al., 2021). The EKE trend
177 computed over high EKE regions from *all-sat* is $5.80 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (or $0.59 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ year}^{-1}$), while from
178 *two-sat* is $2.50 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (or $0.26 \text{ J m}^{-3} \text{ year}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B, C), i.e., 2.3 times smaller (Fig. 3C). These
179 EKE trends represent an increase per decade of 5.7% for *all-sat* and 2.5% for *two-sat*, relative to

180 their respective mean EKE values (Table S1). Assuming a surface area of $1.65 \times 10^7 \text{ km}^2$, the
181 area-integrated EKE trend is $0.10 \times 10^{15} \text{ J m}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ for *all-sat* and $0.04 \times 10^{15} \text{ J m}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$
182 for *two-sat*. A previous study reported an EKE increase rate of 2.5% per decade from *all-sat*
183 vDT2018, with a different definition of high EKE regions (Martínez-Moreno et al., 2021).

184 In high EKE regions the sensitivity test of *two-sat* shows a progressive increase of the EKE trends
185 computed over the periods evaluated (Fig. 3B, blue bars). The sensitivity test of *all-sat* also
186 shows a progressive increase of EKE trends (Fig. 3B, red bars), but this increase is smaller due to
187 the time-dependent limitations of *all-sat* explained in the previous section. Because of this, we
188 focus here the discussion on the results obtained from *two-sat*. Over the last 20 years the *two-*
189 *sat* EKE trend is slightly higher than that computed over the complete 30 years of altimetry
190 data, but afterwards the trend increases to a maximum of $14.9 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for the period 2012-
191 2022, which is 6.0 times larger than the trend computed over 1993-2022. This means that the
192 ocean mesoscale variability is becoming more energetic in high EKE regions than in other
193 regions of the world ocean (Fig. S4), and the pace of this increase of energy is faster over the
194 last decade (Fig. 3).

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202 **Fig. 4. Sensitivity test over the Kuroshio Extension and the Gulf Stream.** EKE trends computed
 203 for the **(A)** Kuroshio Extension and **(B)** Gulf Stream over different periods. Trends are computed
 204 from the original area-weighted mean EKE time series shown in Fig. S5. Statistically significant
 205 trends ($p < 0.05$) are represented by solid-colored bars, while non-significant trends are
 206 represented as bars with oblique lines. Standard errors for *all-sat* (*two-sat*) trends are shown
 207 with yellow (blue) error bars.

208 An examination of specific high EKE regions (Fig. S5, S6, 4) reveals that the domains with
 209 statistically significant positive EKE trends for both altimetric products and maintained over the
 210 periods evaluated in the sensitivity test are the Kuroshio Extension (Fig. 4A) and the Gulf
 211 Stream (Fig. 4B; with the exception of the *two-sat* 1993-2022 and 1994-2022 trends, that are
 212 not statistically significant). In the Kuroshio Extension, with both altimetric products we obtain

213 similar EKE trends, being the ratio between the *all-sat* trend and the *two-sat* trend 1.2 for the
214 period 1993-2022 and 0.9 between 2013 and 2022 (Fig. 4A). This suggests that in this region the
215 impact of the varying number of satellites used to build *all-sat* is smaller than in the other
216 regions, or even negligible, and that *two-sat*, with smaller resolution, is able to capture the
217 magnitude of the increasing trends. Over the last 30 years, the EKE trends in the Kuroshio
218 Extension are $9.70 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *all-sat* and $8.31 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *two-sat*, while over the last 10
219 years these trends are $55.96 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and $59.73 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. 4A). This result
220 indicates that over the last decade the EKE in the Kuroshio Extension has increased 6 to 7 times
221 faster than over the last three decades. The EKE trends computed over the altimetric era
222 represent an increase per decade relative to their respective mean values (Table S1) of 9.3% for
223 *all-sat* and 8.1% for *two-sat*, while the EKE trends computed for the last decade represent an
224 increase of 54% and 58%, respectively. In addition, the Kuroshio Extension is the high EKE
225 region with the largest trends from both altimetric products (Fig. S5, S6, 4). A poleward
226 migration and intensification of the Kuroshio Extension system has been previously reported
227 from datasets that use the *all-sat* altimetric product and from climate models, revealing a
228 relation between the EKE evolution and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (Yang C. et al., 2023;
229 Yang H. et al., 2016). The analysis of EKE trends conducted here corroborates the intensification
230 detected previously in the Kuroshio Extension.

231 The Gulf Stream is the second region with the largest EKE trends (Fig. S5, S6, 4). Over the last
232 three decades, the EKE trends are $7.06 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *all-sat* and a statistically non-significant
233 $2.27 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *two-sat*, representing a ratio of 3.1 (Fig. 4B). These trends increase to 24.50
234 $\text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *all-sat* and $19.20 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *two-sat* (both trends are statistically significant)
235 over the last decade, showing a reduction in the ratio to 1.3 (similar to the result obtained for
236 the global ocean, Fig. 3C). This indicates that in the Gulf Stream the *two-sat* EKE trend has
237 increased 8.5 times faster over the last decade than over the complete altimetric era (Fig. 4B),
238 and that the *all-sat* EKE trend evolution may be affected by the varying number of satellites
239 (see the discussion for the global ocean). The EKE trends computed over the last 30 years
240 represent an increase per decade relative to their respective mean values (Table S1) of 6.5% for
241 *all-sat* and 2.1% (statistically non-significant) for *two-sat*, while the EKE trends computed over

242 the last decade represent an increase of 23% and 18%, respectively. A positive, consistent and
243 increasing EKE trend in the Gulf Stream is a new result that contrasts with previous climate
244 studies. The Gulf Stream contributes to the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC)
245 and is also the western boundary current of the subtropical North Atlantic gyre circulation. The
246 AMOC plays a crucial role in regulating Earth's climate and is constituted by the Gulf Stream,
247 that transports warm and saline Atlantic water polewards, the cooling and densification of this
248 water in the Nordic Seas, and the return of the cooled water at depth (Buckley et al., 2016).
249 Previous climate studies reported a weakening of the AMOC (e.g. Caesar et al., 2018; van
250 Westen et al., 2024). Our study raises a new question regarding how the observed
251 strengthening of the Gulf Stream mesoscale variability influences the temporal evolution of the
252 AMOC. In the Southern Ocean, experiments with high-resolution ocean models reveal that
253 mesoscale eddies may mitigate the effects of a warming climate by maintaining the strength of
254 the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (Munday et al., 2013) and delaying the decline of Antarctic
255 sea ice (Rackow et al., 2022). These processes, together with the increase of EKE detected in
256 the Gulf Stream, occur at scales smaller than those resolved in climate models. Additionally,
257 submesoscale dynamics, not resolved by nadir altimeters, may transfer kinetic energy to
258 mesoscale eddies, contributing to the reported EKE intensification (e.g. Qiu et al., 2024). To
259 study the impact of small-scale ocean processes in the large-scale climate system we need to
260 better represent them in climate models and projections, or use alternative approaches (Hewitt
261 et al., 2022). In addition, the relationship between the Gulf Stream, the AMOC and the
262 subtropical North Atlantic gyre is complex and makes necessary a sustained long-term
263 observation of the ocean and the development of novel techniques to analyze all available data
264 comprehensively (Volkov et al., 2024). The study conducted here highlights the importance of
265 analyzing the relation between the strengthening of the mesoscale variability in the Gulf
266 Stream and the temporal evolution of the subtropical North Atlantic gyre and AMOC.

267 Chi et al. (2021) evaluated 26 years of along-track altimetric data (1993–2018) to determine if
268 the expected deceleration and poleward shift of the Gulf Stream by climate predictions were
269 observable. They calculated linear trends in several metrics (latitude, transport, width and
270 maximum downstream velocity) in stream-following coordinates and concluded that the trends

271 were not significant. They also mentioned that the only locations with trend confidence showed
272 that the Gulf Stream had accelerated and narrowed. Another study based on satellite
273 observations revealed a correlation between mesoscale variability and the Gulf Stream
274 meridional position (Guo et al., 2023). A more energetic mesoscale field was associated with a
275 northward shift of the Gulf Stream position and with a positive North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO).

276 A recent study by Sánchez-Román et al. (2024) provides additional insight into Gulf Stream
277 dynamics. They examined 30 years of altimetric data (1993–2022) and an ocean reanalysis
278 product to investigate the evolution of the Gulf Stream destabilization point—the location
279 where the stable jet transitions into an unstable, meandering path. They observed a significant
280 westward and southward shift of the destabilization point until 2012, followed by a reversal to
281 an eastward and northward migration through 2022. This northeastward migration was
282 associated with an increase in EKE and an acceleration of surface geostrophic velocities. Their
283 analysis revealed a strong correlation between the displacement of the destabilization point
284 and NAO variability, indicating that the Gulf Stream path may respond to NAO-driven changes
285 over time. The findings by Sánchez-Román et al. (2024) align with our results in the Gulf Stream.
286 Together, these studies highlight the dynamic nature of the Gulf Stream system and its
287 sensitivity to both internal variability and external forcing. This reinforces the need for
288 continued monitoring to understand how Gulf Stream dynamics may evolve under future
289 climate scenarios.

290 The positive and increasing EKE trends obtained in the Kuroshio Extension and the Gulf Stream
291 are in opposition to the non-significant trends reported by Martínez-Moreno et al. (2021) from
292 the *all-sat* vDT2018 altimetric product (their Fig. 6 in Extended Data). A possible reason for this
293 difference may be the distinct methodologies followed to define the high EKE regions. They
294 define them with the 99th percentile of the mean kinetic energy (computed from the time-
295 mean velocity field), while we use the 90th spatial percentile on the mean EKE field. We have
296 compared the boundaries obtained from each methodology and found negligible differences
297 (Fig. S7). Hence, the discrepancy between results comes from the older version of the altimetric
298 product that they used and the shorter time series that was available at that moment. As the

299 time series expands and the altimetric products are improved in the future, it will be necessary
300 to reevaluate the analysis of the EKE trends conducted here to determine if our results remain
301 consistent over time.

302 Beech et al. (2022) analyzed the long-term evolution of EKE using a climate model with
303 variable-resolution aimed at increasing grid precision in high EKE regions. That model has the
304 knowledgeable limitations of (i) underrepresenting the EKE with respect to altimetric observations
305 (especially in high latitudes) and (ii) representing a North Atlantic EKE distribution more zonal
306 than observed by satellite altimetry (their Fig. 2). In that study EKE is projected to shift
307 poleward in several high EKE regions, to increase in the Kuroshio Current and to decrease in the
308 Gulf Stream. However, their EKE representation in the Kuroshio Current is more similar to
309 altimetric observations than the EKE representation in the Gulf Stream, which is smaller in
310 magnitude, particularly in the northern part, and differs in position. They show that the Gulf
311 Stream is projected to decrease in eddy activity over the twenty-first century, in opposition to
312 the result obtained here from 30 years of satellite altimetry. This discrepancy is likely
313 attributable to the limitations of the climate model over the North Atlantic.

314 **Conclusions**

315 We have investigated the Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE) temporal evolution to evaluate if the
316 surface global ocean is becoming more energetic through the analysis of 30 years of satellite
317 altimetry observations (1993-2022). Ocean mesoscale variability is a key component of the
318 global ocean circulation and includes fronts, meanders and eddies on spatial scales between
319 ~10-100 km. The EKE associated with these features accounts for about 90% of the total kinetic
320 energy of the oceans (Ferrari and Wunsch, 2009; Wunsch, 2007). We have computed EKE
321 trends from two altimetric products: *all-sat* includes all available altimetry data and is
322 constructed to study mesoscale dynamics, while *two-sat* considers a consistent number of
323 satellites and is built for climate applications. The globally-averaged EKE time series over the
324 altimetric era (1993-2022) show statistically significant positive trends, with the *all-sat* product
325 indicating a larger increase compared to the *two-sat* product. Our results suggest that the
326 increasing number of satellites in the altimetric record may partly contribute to the observed

327 differences. Despite this, both altimetric products support the conclusion that the global ocean
328 mesoscale variability is strengthening, and this intensification is concentrated in regions
329 characterized by high EKE levels.

330 Robust statistically significant positive EKE trends are observed in the Kuroshio Extension and
331 the Gulf Stream. The Kuroshio Extension has the largest EKE trends from both altimetric
332 products. Over the last three decades, the EKE trends in the Kuroshio Extension are $9.70 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$
333 y^{-1} for *all-sat* and $8.31 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *two-sat*, indicating an intensification of EKE of $\sim 8\text{-}9\%$ per
334 decade with respect to mean values. The trends in this region are similar for both datasets,
335 suggesting that the impact of the varying number of satellites used to build *all-sat* is smaller
336 than in the other regions. Over the last decade, the EKE in the Kuroshio Extension has increased
337 6 to 7 times faster than over the last three decades, representing an increase of $\sim 50\%$ with
338 respect to mean values. These findings support previous studies that detected an intensification
339 of the Kuroshio Extension, potentially linked to the Pacific Decadal Oscillation.

340 The Gulf Stream is the second region with the largest EKE trends. Over the altimetric era, the
341 EKE trends in the Gulf Stream are $7.06 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *all-sat* and a statistically non-significant
342 $2.27 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ for *two-sat* (note that for *two-sat* non-significant trends are obtained only for
343 the periods 1993-2022 and 1994-2022, being significant for all the other periods evaluated in
344 the sensitivity test), representing an increase per decade relative to their respective mean
345 values of 6.5% for *all-sat* and 2.1% for *two-sat*. Over the last decade, this region has increased
346 8.5 times faster than over the complete altimetric era, representing a statistically significant
347 increase of $\sim 20\%$ with respect to mean values. A positive, consistent and increasing EKE trend in
348 the Gulf Stream opens new questions about its relationship with the Atlantic meridional
349 overturning circulation (AMOC) and the subtropical North Atlantic gyre. Sustained long-term
350 observation of the ocean and the development of novel techniques to analyze all available data
351 exhaustively are necessary to study the complex relationship between the Gulf Stream, the
352 AMOC and the subtropical North Atlantic gyre.

353 The observed strengthening of mesoscale variability in the Gulf Stream challenges existing
354 climate model projections. Our findings emphasize the need for improved representation of

355 small-scale ocean processes in climate models to better understand their influence on the
356 large-scale climate system. A comprehensive analysis of the dynamics driving changes in
357 mesoscale variability is necessary to discern anthropogenic change from natural variability. Our
358 results are also relevant for studies that use models with assimilation of observations or that
359 rely on observations for their validation, as considering an expanding set of observations over
360 time may lead to overestimated trends (Wunsch, 2020).

361 As the altimetric record increases and future advancements enhance altimetric products, it will
362 be necessary to reassess the analysis of EKE trends conducted here to verify the consistency of
363 our findings over time. The Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) mission (Morrow et
364 al., 2019; Fu et al., 2024) provides high-resolution altimetric observations that offer
365 unprecedented opportunities to investigate the contribution of submesoscale processes to the
366 observed intensification of EKE (Archer et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024). Validation of SWOT
367 data through multi-platform in situ observations is essential to ensure the accuracy of EKE
368 estimates at these small scales (Pascual et al., 2023; Verger-Miralles et al., 2024; Barceló-Llull
369 and Pascual, 2023). The long-term maintenance of the altimetric satellite constellation will be
370 crucial to evaluate EKE trends and better understand the evolving energetics of the global
371 ocean.

372

373

374 **Data and Methods**

375 **1 Altimetry data products**

376 In this study, we use the latest version of the global multi-satellite Delayed Time (DT) Data
377 Unification and Altimeter Combination System (DUACS) (Pujol et al., 2023; Taburet et al., 2021),
378 named vDT2021 and freely available through the European Copernicus Program
379 (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/>). The vDT2021 product supersedes the previous vDT2018
380 version when comparing with independent in situ observations (Taburet et al., 2019). The

381 DUACS system generates two distinct types of altimetric Level-4 (L4) gridded products for the
382 global ocean: the *all-sat* and the *two-sat* products. The *all-sat* product (Pujol et al., 2023),
383 disseminated via the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) project (Product ID:
384 SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_L4_MY_008_047; doi: <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00148>), incorporates
385 all available altimeters at a given time, ranging from 2 to 7 over the altimetric period (Fig. S1). It
386 emphasizes the mesoscale mapping capacity of the altimeter data and the stability of the
387 overall dataset, despite the time-variable errors dependent on the number of satellites used
388 (Pujol et al., 2023). The *two-sat* product (Taburet et al., 2021), distributed via the Copernicus
389 Climate Change Service (C3S) project and also by CMEMS (Product ID:
390 SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_CLIMATE_L4_MY_008_057; doi: <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00145>), is
391 derived from a consistent pair of altimeters, which is considered the minimum requirement for
392 retrieving mesoscale signals in delayed time conditions (Pascual et al., 2006). The *two-sat*
393 product is mainly based on the long-term TOPEX/POSEIDON/Jason orbit and completed by a
394 second mission on the ERS/Envisat/AltiKa or the more recent Sentinel-3 orbit (Morrow et al.,
395 2023). This product prioritizes the stability of the global mean sea level, assuming the cost of
396 reducing the spatial coverage of the ocean. The steady number of altimeters ensures nearly
397 consistent errors throughout the entire time period, barring minor variations due to changes in
398 the satellite constellation (Pujol et al., 2023). The *two-sat* product is aimed at monitoring the
399 long-term evolution of sea level, therefore it is appropriate for climate studies of sea level
400 (large-scale signals) (Taburet et al., 2019).

401 The validation of altimetry products is a fundamental step in the DUACS data processing to
402 assess and characterize the errors associated with the altimetry measurements (Sánchez-
403 Román et al., 2023). The quality of both *all-sat* and *two-sat* altimetric products is mainly
404 assessed through the analysis of the sea level anomaly (SLA) field at different steps of the
405 processing and through the evaluation of the SLA consistency along the tracks of different
406 altimeters and between gridded and along-track products, in addition to comparisons with
407 external in situ measurements (Pujol et al., 2023).

408 Both the *all-sat* and *two-sat* products provide geostrophic velocity anomalies derived from the

409 gridded SLA field, which is calculated with respect to a temporal mean of sea surface height
410 over the same period (1993-2012; Pujol et al., 2023). The geostrophic velocity anomalies
411 provided by the altimetric products represent ocean currents at the surface and are computed
412 through the application of the geostrophic approximation by using a 9-point stencil width
413 methodology (Arbic et al., 2012) for latitudes outside the $\pm 5^\circ\text{N}$ band. In the equatorial band,
414 they are computed through the Lagerloef methodology (Lagerloef et al., 1999) with the β plane
415 approximation. Both the *all-sat* and *two-sat* data products cover the period ranging from 1
416 January 1993 to 7 June 2023 (last accessed in March 2024) and have a spatio-temporal
417 resolution of $1/4^\circ$ and 1 day. To study the temporal evolution of the EKE we analyze data from
418 complete years, i.e., from 1993 to 2022.

419 **2 Eddy Kinetic Energy computation**

420 The calculation of the Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE) is performed with the following expression:

$$421 \quad \text{EKE} = \frac{1}{2} \rho (u_a^2 + v_a^2),$$

422 where $\rho = 1025 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ is the constant approximated sea water density, and u_a and v_a are the
423 zonal and meridional geostrophic velocity anomalies, respectively, provided by the altimetric
424 products. The EKE SI units are J m^{-3} . However, we will be working instead with the EKE
425 normalized by the density, whose units are $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, as done by the altimetric community. The
426 relation between the two conventions is a constant factor:

$$427 \quad \text{EKE} [\text{J m}^{-3}] \sim 0.1025 \cdot \text{normalized EKE} [\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}].$$

428 Hereinafter, the normalized EKE will be called EKE. The EKE is computed from the geostrophic
429 velocity anomaly fields, and therefore it represents the kinetic energy associated with
430 deviations from the mean oceanic flow.

431 To compute the mean EKE and the EKE trends, an ice mask is implemented to systematically
432 exclude regions covered by ice throughout the annual cycle. Thus, the analysis is confined to
433 latitudes between 65°N and 65°S , where the ocean remains mostly ice-free throughout the

434 year, ensuring consistent, uninterrupted satellite altimetry measurements.

435 To calculate spatial averages of EKE, we compute the area-weighted arithmetic mean with the
436 following equation:

$$437 \quad \overline{\text{EKE}} = \frac{\sum_{i,j} [\text{area}_{i,j} \cdot \text{EKE}_{i,j}]}{\sum_{i,j} \text{area}_{i,j}},$$

438 where $\text{area}_{i,j}$ is the area of each grid cell within the selected region, i represents indices along
439 the longitude axis, and j represents indices along the latitude axis.

440 **3 Definition of high EKE regions**

441 In this study, we delineate areas characterized by high EKE, hereinafter referred to as high EKE
442 regions (see Fig. 1). They are identified as those regions exceeding the 90th spatial percentile
443 on the mean EKE field computed over the period 1993-2022 from the *all-sat* data product. To
444 avoid the potential inclusion of small patches with high EKE, we adopt a filtering process
445 consisting of selecting only large and well-defined regions (roughly above $4 \cdot 10^5$ km² in area),
446 resulting in high EKE regions only covering 5% of the global ocean. These regions coincide with
447 the Gulf Stream, the Kuroshio Extension, the Agulhas Current, the Brazil-Malvinas Confluence
448 region, the Loop Current, the Great Whirl and Socotra Eddy in East Africa, and the East
449 Australian Current (Fig. 1).

450 **4 Computation of EKE trends**

451 EKE trends have been computed using the Theil–Sen estimator, while the statistical significance
452 has been calculated with the modified Mann–Kendall test, which accounts for autocorrelations
453 within the time series (Yue and Wang, 2004). The standard errors of the EKE trends have been
454 calculated as the residual standard error divided by the square root of the sum of squared
455 differences in the independent variable (James et al., 2023), considering the effective sample
456 size of the time series from the modified Mann–Kendall test (Yue and Wang, 2004; Martínez-
457 Moreno et al., 2021).

458 **Data availability**

459 The altimetric data products used in this study are publicly available via the following links. The
460 vDT2021 *all-sat* product is available at the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) website via
461 <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00148> (Product ID: SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_L4_MY_008_047). The
462 vDT2021 *two-sat* product is available at the CMEMS website via [https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-](https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00145)
463 [00145](https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00145) (Product ID: SEALEVEL_GLO_PHY_CLIMATE_L4_MY_008_057). The vDT2018 *two-sat*
464 product is available at the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) website via
465 <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.4c328c78>.

466 **Code availability**

467 The Python codes and Jupyter Notebooks to reproduce or extend this study are publicly
468 available on GitHub via https://github.com/bbarcelollull/Global_EKE_trends_from_altimetry.

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648 **Author contributions**

649 A. P., B. B.-L., P. R., V. C. and A. S. R. conceived the study. B. B.-L. and P. R. conducted the
650 analyses. All authors contributed to the interpretation of the results. B. B.-L. wrote the first
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652 **Additional information**

653 Authors declare that they have no competing interests.

654 Supporting Information.

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